

NON-COHESIVE LUNAR REGOLITH–TOOL INTERACTION MODELING FOR SURFACE ACTIVITY DESIGN AND OPERATIONS

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The upcoming lunar surface activities would benefit from predictive numerical tools to support the design and operation of equipment interacting with regolith, whose highly granular, thermally varying, abrasiveness and electrostatically active nature strongly affect robotics performance and systems operability [7]. This work presents a GPU-accelerated multi-physics framework, developed at PoliMi's ASTRA Lab on the DEM-Engine platform [1][2], to model non-cohesive planetary regolith within a digital twin environment for tool-soil interaction on airless bodies. The framework is intended to provide high-fidelity numerical replicas of expected in situ operations, supporting both technology assessment before hardware implementation and mission operations.

The mechanical interaction is based on the Hertz-Mindlin contact model already implemented in DEM-Engine [1][2] and here extended through the coupling with thermal and electrostatic effects. In this framework, the regolith is described as a granular medium whose response depends not only on contact mechanics, but also on environmental conditions that are particularly relevant on the lunar surface [3][4]. Grain charging is initialized and evolved by accounting for photoemission, solar wind, and galactic cosmic rays, so that the electrical state of the soil can vary as a function of local exposure and sub-surface conditions [5].

Figure 1: charge distribution during daytime condition

At the same time, grain temperature is updated through radiative exchange and contact conduction, allowing the model to capture the thermal gradients [6] that naturally develop within the terrain. The soil is represented as an assembly of clumped particles, with layer-dependent physical properties assigned consistently with the thermal and electrostatic condi-

tions expected on the lunar surface. Representative environmental states can, therefore, be simulated and how variations in temperature, charge distribution, and local mechanical properties affect the interaction between regolith and engineering artifacts can be investigated. In particular, the coupled formulation is intended to highlight the role of electrostatic activity in modifying interparticle behavior and soil adhesion, which are key aspects for understanding the operability of tools and mobility systems in lunar conditions.

A simulation campaign is being developed to investigate how terrain properties and artifact characteristics influence soil-tool interaction under lunar environmental conditions, with the goal of classifying the response according to environmental features and tool design parameters. The framework is being applied to wheel-soil and drill-soil interaction scenarios, with particular attention to the combined role of mechanical response and electrostatic adhesion.

Figure 2: wheel-soil interaction during daytime conditions

For drilling applications, the model is intended to capture not only penetration mechanics, but also regolith adhesion effects during tool extraction, which are especially relevant in low-gravity and electrostatically active environments. Soil collection scenarios are also being considered, with experimental comparison foreseen to support future validation of the model mechanical response. These capabilities make the framework suitable for supporting the design of excavation, sampling, manipulation, mobility, and surface operation systems for the incoming lunar missions. The tool is being tuned against experimental results run in lab in relevant environment.

In parallel, a fluid-regolith interaction model is under development to describe the response of granular media to fluid infiltration and gas-driven disturbances. This extension is relevant to in situ resource utilization applications as well as to planetary landing and surface contamination scenarios, where gas-soil coupling may alter the local terrain response. Although the present work focuses on the lunar environment, the overall modeling strategy is conceived as a flexible and extensible framework that can be generalized to other airless or low-atmosphere planetary bodies.

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